

Highlights

- Li-RHC ($2\text{LiH}+\text{MgB}_2/2\text{LiBH}_4+\text{MgH}_2$) composite doped with TiO_2 (Li-RHC-Ti).
- Dual ability of Li-RHC-Ti to purify CO-H_2 and to reduce this CO into CH_4 .
- Hydrides-CO systems for the preparation of gas mixtures based on CH_4 .
- Fast and stable dynamic cycling under a $\text{H}_2\text{-CO}$ (0.1 mol %) releasing 10 wt.% H_2 .
- Formation of MgO , LiBO_2 and HCOO^- after Li-RHC-Ti and CO interactions.

Dual application of Ti-catalyzed Li-RHC composite for H₂ purification and CO methanation

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ABSTRACT

2LiH+MgB₂ composite doped with TiO₂ (Li-RHC-Ti) is employed with a two-fold purpose: hydrogen purification under a H₂-CO (0.1 mol %) mixture and CO methanation. Upon dynamic cycling under CO-H₂ mixture, hydrogen release curves display a quite stable amount of pure hydrogen of about 10 wt%, short release times of around 60 min, and minor degradation. Gas analysis by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) after a thermal dehydrogenation process of MgH₂ and LiBH₄ under CO evidence the conversion of CO to CH₄. Li-RHC-Ti dehydrogenated under CO shows the simultaneous formation of CH₄, CH₃OH, and B(CH₃)₃ in the gas phase. X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) and FTIR characterizations of the solid phases of Li-RHC-Ti after both H₂-CO mixture and CO interactions demonstrate the formation of MgO, LiBO₂, and HCOO⁻ species. Li-RHC-Ti acts as a hydrogen source and promoter for the CO conversion. Reaction pathways are proposed based on experimental results and equilibrium composition calculations.

Keywords: Complex Hydrides; Purification; Methanation; Reactive Hydride Composite, Hydrogen

1. Introduction

Hydrogen is a clean and renewable energy source [1]. According to the expected industrial perspectives for 2025, the hydrogen production market will increase,

encouraged by the demand for the use of cleaner energy, such as vehicles with gas-based fuel cells, and by favorable government regulations [2]. Hydrogen is produced primarily from fossil fuels and other alternative routes, such as the electrolysis of water or the use of photobioreactors [3–6]. The technology commonly used in the hydrogen production processes is steam reforming or partial oxidation of natural gases. In the processes that use fossil fuels as hydrogen raw material, minor amounts of contaminants such as CO, CO₂, H₂O, and sulfur compounds are obtained simultaneously as a consequence. For its use in a fuel cell, hydrogen purity is a crucial issue, and it is usually purified to eliminate contaminants and/or impurities [6,7].

While renewable energy sources are inserted as part of our socio-economical system, a smooth transition towards renewable energy vector driven society is unavoidable. Thus, the development of flexible Power-to-Gas and Power-to-Liquid processes for the clean production of currently used energy carriers represents a smart solution for the transition. The energy produced by renewable sources during the low spot energy price periods can be used to reduce H₂O (or H₂O+CO₂) to H₂ or synthetic gas, i.e. H₂+CO, in an electrolyzer or co-electrolyzer, respectively. The synthetic gas can be used as feedstock for synthetic fuels and synthetic chemical production *via* the Fischer-Tropsch process. This allows smartly couple the two major energy infrastructures of our modern society, i.e. gas and electricity networks while covering the necessities of the mobile sector and several industrial demands of feedstock [8,9].

Several metal hydrides have been extensively studied as hydrogen storage materials [10–13]. Since metal hydrides turn out to be safe hydrogen storage materials that selectively absorb hydrogen at a specific temperature and pressure, their use for the separation and/or purification of hydrogen from a gas mixture with impurities would be possible. Therefore, different kinds of hydrides have been investigated for purification of hydrogen from gas mixtures containing impurities as CO, N₂, CO₂, O₂. The main materials studied for separation/purification of hydrogen are related to AB₅-type Laves phases and some AB₂-type alloys [14–26]. However, there are fewer investigations regarding the application of simple metal hydrides and complex hydrides for hydrogen purification. In the past, MgH₂-based materials were explored as possible materials for

hydrogen purification. The hydrogenation/dehydrogenation properties of MgH₂-V composite during cycling under hydrogen-containing carbon monoxide (110 ppm) were evaluated [27]. The MgH₂-V composite showed deterioration on both sorption kinetics and hydrogen storage capacity after prolonged cycling with CO as an impurity. These effects were related to grain surface structure defects and the presence of CO, reducing the activity of the vanadium catalyst due to the formation of MgO_x phases.

In 2007, the first study using amide as a purification system of CO₂-H₂ rich mixtures produced by natural gas reforming was presented. Hu and Ruckenstein studied the interaction between H₂ and CO₂ with Li₃N [28] and LiNH₂-Li₃N [29] as hydrogen storage systems. These authors reported that the CO₂ (20%)-H₂(80%) mixture could be used as a pure hydrogen source for hydrogen storage in a Li-N-H system because the presence of CO₂ had not changed the hydrogen storage properties.

The most recent investigations using amides for hydrogen purification and storage were published by Sun's group and by our group [30–33]. Sun *et al.* studied the effect of various contaminants such as N₂, CH₄, O₂, and CO on the 2LiNH₂-MgH₂ storage system. It was found that impurities as N₂ and CH₄ do not affect neither the hydrogen desorption properties nor the phase structure of the Li-Mg-N-H system. However, other impurities affected: 2LiNH₂-MgH₂ lost hydrogen storage capacity when a mixture of O₂ (0.1 mol %)-H₂ was used due to the formation of LiNH₂ and MgO on the surface of the particle [30]. Furthermore, CO (1 mol %) impurity negatively affected the hydrogen storage properties of this system [31,32]. Already after 5-6 cycles, the dehydrogenation rate decreased, and a loss in the storage capacity was observed, produced by the irreversible loss of [NH₂]⁻ and the MgO formation. The loss of [NH₂]⁻ groups due to the formation of Li₂CN₂ and KCN caused that the hydrogen capacity and hydrogen desorption kinetics could not be restored to its initial level when purified hydrogen was used again [31,32].

Our last results [33] showed that the CO(0.1 mol%)-H₂ mixture made a positive effect on the dehydrogenation rate of the doped Mg(NH₂)₂-2LiH composite after 20 cycles. However, simultaneous and progressive degradation of the hydrogen storage capacity of this material was observed. The formation of Li₂CN₂ and MgO was mainly responsible

for the deterioration of the hydrogen storage properties due to the reaction between pure CO and the dehydrogenated product $\text{Li}_2\text{Mg}(\text{NH})_2$. This interaction was demonstrated with specially designed experiments for the first time. A reactivity order of CO with $\text{LiNH}_2\text{-LiH}$, $\text{Mg}(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{-2LiH}$, and LiBH_4 systems had been established: $[\text{NH}]^{2-} > [\text{NH}_2]^- > [\text{BH}_4]^-$.

We also reported the possibility of employing metal complex hydrides (Mg_2FeH_6 and Mg_2NiH_4) for the production of a synthetic fuel such as CH_4 from CO_2 [34,35]. We demonstrated that metal complex hydrides synthesized via different routes (thermal processes and mechanical milling) are able to act as hydrogen sources and active species for the production of CH_4 . Different methanation mechanisms were obtained depending on of the nature of the complex hydride, its microstructure, $\text{H}_2\text{:CO}_2$ mol ratio and experimental conditions. Fe particles promotes the total CO_2 conversion via a combination of reverse water shift reaction followed by methanation of CO in presence of steam at 400 °C for 5 h [34]. Under same experimental conditions, Mg_2NiH_4 leads to the incomplete transformation of CO_2 via direct reduction of CO_2 by MgH_2 due to the poisoning of Ni catalyst [34]. In contrast, nanometric Mg_2NiH_4 assists the CO_2 conversion in short time in comparison with micrometric Mg_2NiH_4 via the adsorption of C and posterior hydrogenation towards CH_4 [35]. In this context, other authors investigated the mechanochemical hydrogenation of CO carried out over nanostructured FeCo- and Mg_2Ni -based catalysts [36]. The FeCo based catalysts displayed CO conversion data similar or better under mechanochemical conditions (at room temperature) that conventional thermal activation conditions (400–800 K). Improvement in the percentage and kinetics of CO conversion over hydrides was observed that allowed them to gain some hints of the reaction mechanism [36].

Lithium hydride composite (Li-RHC), i.e., $2\text{LiH}+\text{MgB}_2$ or $2\text{LiBH}_4+\text{MgH}_2$ stoichiometric hydride mixture, has been extensively investigated as a hydrogen storage material for practical applications. Li-RHC has a suitable theoretical reaction enthalpy of 46 kJ/mol H_2 , high storage capacity, and an excellent life cycle [12,37–42]. Nevertheless, the dehydrogenation proceeds in two stages according to the reactions (1) and (2), leading to larger enthalpy values [43].

The first stage of the reaction is fast, while the decomposition of LiBH_4 for the formation of MgB_2 is quite slow. Thus, the system has slow kinetic behavior, and for this reason, additives to speed up mainly the second reaction step are required [37,38].

Several studies were done using different additives to improve the hydrogen storage properties of the Li-RHC system. Additives such as transition metals and transition metal compounds (TM-compounds) via the formation of transition metal borides (TM-borides) [44–46], and nanosized TM-borides [47–54] were investigated. Also, the nanoconfinement method, as doped in Li-RHC material, was carried out [55–58]. These catalysts significantly improve the kinetic properties of the system. However, TM-compounds such as halides generate by-products, reducing the hydrogen capacity.

Puszkiet *et al.*[51] showed the effect of the TiO_2 addition to Li-RHC composite and the *in situ* formation of core-shell Li_xTiO_2 nanoparticles. The kinetic behavior and the cycling stability have been noticeably improved with 1 mol % of TiO_2 to Li-RHC. Considering the interesting hydrogen storage properties of catalyzed Li-RHC, the effect of 0.1 mol% of CO in a rich H_2 mixture on the hydrogen storage properties of Li-RHC is investigated in this work. The nature of the interactions between CO and the components of the Li-RHC are here clarified. To the best of our knowledge, the catalytic interaction between Li-RHC and CO has not been reported so far. Furthermore, the main advantages and disadvantages regarding the application of this complex hydride system as hydrogen purification and methanation medium are discussed.

2. Experimental

2.1 Synthesis of the $2\text{LiH} + \text{MgB}_2$ composite with additive

LiH (Aldrich, 95 %, 30 mesh), MgB_2 (Alfa Aesar, 325 mesh) and TiO_2 (Aldrich, 99.99 %) were used as reactants. All materials were handled in a MBraun Unilab argon-filled box, under oxygen and moisture-controlled atmosphere (both levels lower than 5 ppm). Lithium reactive hydride composite $2\text{LiH} + \text{MgB}_2$ was prepared with TiO_2 (1 mol %) as

additive [51] by mechanical milling (MM) for 2 h using a sequence of 15 min milling and 5 min pause. The milling was done in a planetary ball mill (Fritsch Pulverisette 6) at 400 rpm under 0.1 MPa of argon, using an 80 cm³ milling chamber and a ball to powder ratio of 40:1. The sample was named as Li-RHC-Ti (lithium reactive hydride composite with TiO₂ as an additive). Gases of high purity were used, hydrogen (Linde, grade 5.0), argon (Linde, grade 5.0), carbon monoxide (0.1 mol%)-hydrogen mixture (Linde, certificate standard), and carbon monoxide (Praxair, grade 4.5).

2.2 Characterization of the composite

The structure of the Li-RHC-Ti composite and the as-cycled samples was analyzed at room temperature by X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD, PANalytical Empyrean, Cu K α radiation, graphite monochromator) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, Perkin Elmer Spectrum 400 with MCT detector).

For XRPD routine patterns, the samples were maintained under Ar atmosphere using a tightly sealed holder. The data were collected over a 2θ angular range between 10-80° with a step size of 0.02° and a collection time of 1 s. For IR spectroscopy measurements, the solid pellets were prepared under Ar atmosphere inside the glove box using dry KBr and a specially designed airtight cell. FTIR analyses of gas released after heating of LiBH₄, MgH₂, and Li-RHC-Ti composite in pure CO atmosphere at room temperature (RT), 200, 300, and 400 °C were performed. A degassed quartz optical cell with KBr windows was used. The FTIR spectra were collected at RT in the range of 4000-800 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ for solid-state and 0.5 cm⁻¹ for the gas. For the FTIR analyses of gas species, the powders were heated up from room temperature to the desired temperature, kept during 15 min with 0.1 MPa of CO, and then collected in a closed quartz reactor. Finally, the gas atmosphere was expanded into a gas-FTIR cell for the analyses.

For hydrogen sorption kinetics of the Li-RHC-Ti, a modified Sieverts-type device with mass flow controllers was used. The samples were manipulated in a glove box and introduced inside a stainless reactor, which was then connected to the Sieverts equipment. First, the dehydrogenated milled sample was heated up to 400 °C (the reaction temperature) under pure H₂ pressure (5.0 MPa) and kept at this temperature for

15 min. Then, up to 15 dehydrogenation/hydrogenation cycles with pure H₂ were measured as a reference. After cycling with pure H₂, hydrogen storage properties of Li-RHC-Ti were evaluated using a CO (0.1 mol%)-H₂ mixture. Hydrogenation curves were obtained at a constant pressure of 5.0 MPa and dehydrogenation curves with gas backpressure of 0.3 MPa, in both cases at 400 °C. Using the dehydrogenation curves, which consist of two stages, the rate values were obtained. The released hydrogen amounts were expressed as wt%, considering the initial total mass. Moreover, to maximize the possible interactions between the hydrogenated states of the Li-RHC-Ti and CO, its hydrides, i.e., LiBH₄ and MgH₂, were heated with pure CO (0.27 MPa) at 5 °C min⁻¹ from RT to 400 °C. The interactions were displayed as the amount of gas consumed or liberated (gas mol/sample mol) as a function of time.

2.3 Thermodynamic calculations

Calculations on the compositions of species as a product of the hydrides-H₂/CO and hydrides-CO interactions under equilibrium conditions were performed with the software HSC Chemistry 9.7 [59]. Mixtures composed of MgH₂-CO, LiBH₄-CO, Li-RHC-CO, and Li-RHC-H₂-0.1mol%CO were considered. Upon dehydrogenation under pure CO, the equilibrium compositions were calculated with the conditions of a ramp of temperature from 25 °C to 400 °C under 0.27 MPa of CO. In the case of isothermal interaction, 5 MPa of H₂-0.1mol% CO and 400 °C were considered. For the isothermal hydrogenation at 400 °C, as initial compositions, the solid species coming from the hydrogenation outcomes and the removal of the generated gas species upon hydrogenation were taken into account. These conditions are similar to the experimental ones. For all the calculations, species such as closo-borohydrides (Li₂B₁₂H₁₂) and different Mg borates or formate species were not involved since they are not available in the database. Moreover, LiBH₄ is considered as solid-phase over all the temperature range. The following phases were taken into account: LiBH₄(s), MgH₂(s), LiH(s), MgB₂(s), H₂(g), O₂(g), CO(g), CO₂(g), CH₄(g), H₂O(g), B₂H₆(g), HCOO(g), B(CH₃)₃, BO₂(g), CH₃OH(g), C(s), LiBO₂(s), Mg(s), and MgO(s).

3. Results

3.1 Purification of H₂: Li-RHC-Ti cycling under CO (0.1mol%)-H₂ mixture

Li-RHC-Ti composite using pure H₂ or the CO (0.1mol%)-H₂ mixture was studied during continuous cycling. The dehydrogenation cycles obtained under 5.0 MPa of pure H₂ or CO-H₂ mixture at 400 °C are shown in Fig.1. Desorption curves performed under pure H₂ show increasing kinetics from the first until the last cycle (15th cycle). From cycle 11th onwards, the change is not so prominent and it can be considered as it reached a constant desorption rate.

A change in the atmosphere from pure H₂ to CO-H₂ mixture results in different behavior for the Li-RHC-Ti. Fig. 1 shows that the presence of CO during cycling leads to a quite reproducible dehydrogenation kinetic curves and the same hydrogen capacity as the ones obtained with pure H₂.

Figure 1: Dehydrogenation curves of the Li-RHC-Ti at 400 °C after rehydrogenation at 5.0 MPa with pure H₂ and CO (0.1 mol %)-H₂ mixture.

To investigate the effect of CO on the hydrogen storage properties, the evolutions of both the amount of hydrogen released (Fig. S1) and the H₂ desorption times, related with the dehydrogenation rates (Fig. 2), for the first and second reaction steps (equations 1 and 2) were evaluated during cycling. The values of hydrogen storage capacity obtained at 90 min in pure H₂ indicate that the capacity remains stable at 10.1 wt% between the cycles 11 and 15. Under the CO-H₂ mixture, the hydrogen storage capacity of the Li-RHC-Ti slightly decreases with the successive hydrogenation-dehydrogenation cycles. Comparing the hydrogen storage capacities at the end of cycling, a relative reduction of about 4 % in the hydrogen capacity occurs between the sample cycled under pure hydrogen (10.1 wt%, cycle 15) and the one cycled under CO-H₂ mixture (9.7 wt%, cycle 11).

The first stage of the H₂ desorption releases 2 wt%, while the second stage releases from 2 wt% till 10 wt% in total. Fig. 2 shows the time required for the release of half of the hydrogen weight percentage corresponding to each dehydrogenation stage for the Li-RHC-Ti (equations 1 and 2), which provides an estimation of the speed of these processes. For the first dehydrogenation stage, this time remains constant under pure H₂, while it slightly increases under CO-H₂ atmosphere. In contrast, a different behavior was found for the required time in the second dehydrogenation stage. The dehydrogenation time needed to release 6 wt% of Li-RHC-Ti cycled under pure H₂ exhibits a large decrease, meaning a faster desorption rate. On the contrary, the dehydrogenation time for the second stage under the CO-H₂ mixture remains practically constant. Therefore, the presence of 0.1% of CO in the atmosphere has a more marked effect in the first stage, while the second remains practically unchanged.

Figure 2: Time required to achieve 1 and 6 wt% H₂ desorption for the first and second stages, respectively, during each cycle for Li-RHC-Ti. The cycles with CO-H₂ mixture were performed after cycling with pure H₂.

3.2 Characterization of the Li-RHC-Ti and CO-H₂ interactions after cycling

To analyze possible changes in the phases after the interaction between Li-RHC-Ti and the CO containing H₂ atmosphere, XRPD and FTIR spectroscopy measurements were carried out. For comparison purposes, all characterizations were performed with the samples cycled under pure H₂ (see Fig. 3 and S2). No modification of the crystalline phases is found in the dehydrogenated samples, regardless of the presence of CO as an impurity. XRPD analyses are in agreement with the main phases involved in equations (1) and (2), and the employed catalyst (Fig.S2) [51].

Fig. 3A shows the XRPD for the Li-RHC-Ti hydrogenated under 5.0 MPa of pure H₂ and CO-H₂ atmosphere, and at different stages of cycling. In all cases, the main peaks belonging to LiBH₄ and MgH₂ along with reflections corresponding to Li-Ti-O catalytic phases are observed. In particular, small peaks coming from the presence of LiH and MgB₂ are detected after the first hydrogen absorption cycle with pure H₂ (Fig. 3Aa). The formation of MgO upon cycling in pure H₂ can be attributed to a small amount of oxygen in the pipelines and/or the fact that the as-purchased MgB₂ already had small amounts of nanocrystalline MgO (Fig. 3Aa,b). After cycling in pure H₂ or CO-H₂ mixture, it is possible to observe broad peaks of MgO at about 43° and 62° of 2θ. Notably, the MgO peaks display higher intensity in the sample hydrogenated in the presence of CO (Fig. 3Ac).

FTIR technique was used to reveal the possible amorphous compounds in the rehydrogenated samples (Fig.3B). Characteristic stretching and bending modes of the B–H bond at 2380, 2288, 2218, 1122, and 1090 cm⁻¹ are identified for both Li-RHC-Ti cycled under pure H₂ and CO-H₂ mixture (Fig.3Ba,b) [53]. These signals are related to the presence of the LiBH₄ composite, in agreement with the XRPD patterns shown in Fig.3A. An additional band due to the B–H bond can be observed at 2489 cm⁻¹ in both samples that correspond to Li₂B₁₂H₁₂ [60]. Some differences appear when Li-RHC-Ti is cycled in the presence of CO (Fig. 3Bb). The intense signals at 3408 and 1628 cm⁻¹ are ascribed to O–H stretching and (H–O–H) bending vibrations of water molecules over solid [61,62]. The presence of formate species can not be discarded because its main band is overlapped with the band of the bending mode of H–O–H. The FTIR bands at 1384 cm⁻¹ and 1122 cm⁻¹ are related with the formation of B–O bond. The main vibrations of B–O can be observed at 1450–1300 cm⁻¹ and 1150–1000 cm⁻¹ due to asymmetric stretching of three and four coordinate boron, respectively [62]. The formation of borate and formate species was previously reported as products of reactions between borohydrides of alkali metals and CO₂ [63,64]. Bands at low frequencies (600–700 cm⁻¹) correspond to boron lattice vibrations [65].

Thus, on the base of the XRD and FTIR studies, the reaction between Li-RHC-Ti and CO(1mol%)/H₂ mixture favors the bulk MgO formation as well as the production of

borate and formate species. These results demonstrate that some type of interaction occurred under cycling in presence of CO.

Figure 3: **A** XRPD patterns for Li-RHC-Ti after (a) 1st hydrogenation under 5.0 MPa H₂, (b) 11th rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa H₂ and (c) 12th rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa CO-H₂. **B** FTIR spectra for Li-RHC-Ti after (a) 11th rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa H₂ and (b) 11th rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa CO-H₂. All hydrogenation curves were obtained at 400 °C.

3.3 Methanation of CO: Reactivity between Li-RHC-Ti and pure CO

In this section, the results obtained from the reaction between pure CO and Li-RHC-Ti, as well as with LiBH₄ and MgH₂ are shown. Aiming to shed light on the interactions between Li-RHC-Ti and H₂-CO mixture upon cycling and to investigate the feasibility to employ Li-RHC as the hydrogen source and catalytic compound for the methanation of CO, specific experiments were planned. Volumetric measurements, XRPD analyses, and FTIR spectra of the gas and solid phases were performed to study the reactions.

The gas-solid reaction of CO with Li-RHC-Ti, LiBH₄ and MgH₂ was followed by using a Sieverts equipment and expressed in terms of gas mol/mol of the sample as a function of temperature (Fig. 4, heating from RT to 400 °C). For the case of the LiBH₄ (Fig. 4b) and MgH₂ (Fig. 4c), samples do not show a relevant variation in the amount of gas absorbed up to 300 °C and 360 °C, respectively. LiBH₄ starts to decompose at about 300 °C after 1 h, releasing a final amount of 0.3 mol of gas mol/mol of the sample. MgH₂

begins its decomposition at about 360 °C after about 1 h and 30 min and provides 0.8 mol of gas mol/mol of the sample at the end of the measurement. In the case of the hydrogenated Li-RHC-Ti (Fig. 4a), a CO absorption of about 0.33 mol of gas/mol of sample is observed in the range of temperature between 200 °C and 320 °C. Then, after reaching about 320 °C, the partial decomposition of Li-RHC-Ti starts, and the entire release amounts to 1 mol of gas/mol of sample.

Figure 4: Gas sorption curves as a function of time during non-isothermal interaction of pure CO with (a) Li-RHC-Ti (hydrogenated state), (b) LiBH₄ and (c) MgH₂. Pressure of 0.27 MPa of CO, average heating ramp: 5 °C min⁻¹ from RT to 400 °C (blue dotted line).

Considering the different behavior of Li-RHC-Ti, LiBH₄, and MgH₂ during heating under CO atmosphere, XRPD (Fig. 5A) and FTIR (Fig. 5B) analysis of the solid phases after the volumetric measurements done with pure CO (Fig. 4) were carried out. It is important

to mention that all samples were in hydrogenated state for the heating experiment under CO atmosphere. For pure LiBH_4 sample (Fig.5Ab), the XRPD pattern clearly shows the characteristic peaks of LiBH_4 , simultaneously with the most intense peaks of LiH . Moreover, between 20° and 30° of 2θ it is possible to see a bump attributed to a containing carbon species. It is not clear whether this bump belongs to Li_2C_2 or LiC_6 species, which has been reported as feasible formed phases under the herein working conditions. Both Li_2C_2 and LiC_6 present intense reflections in the above mentioned 2θ , but it seems that they are not in crystalline state, they are in a quite small amount and furthermore peaks of LiBH_4 also present in the same 2θ range [66,67]. Other observable small reflections in the XRPD for LiBH_4 after the heating ramp under CO (Fig. 5Ab) are in the 2θ range between 15° and 18° . These small peaks might come from the presence of crystalline lithium *closo*-borate $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ taking as a reference the work of Pitt et al. [68]. NMR measurements indicated the presence of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ after milling and hydrogen interaction for Li-RHC added $3\text{TiCl}_3\cdot\text{AlCl}_3$, but not in crystalline state [69]. FTIR analyses (Fig. 5B) provides additional information about the carbon and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ species. In the case of MgH_2 , the XRPD pattern (Fig. 5Ac) mainly shows the presence of Mg phase, while the most intense diffraction peaks of MgO and MgH_2 are also observable. Thus, it is possible to find agreement between the volumetric measurement (Fig. 4c) and the detected crystalline phases based on the XRPD patterns: the decomposition of MgH_2 leads to the formation of Mg as the main final phase, while the CO presence induces partial oxidation of MgH_2/Mg to MgO . In the case of the reactive hydride composite exposed to CO, in addition to the presence of the starting materials (LiBH_4 and MgH_2), the formation of Mg , MgB_2 , and MgO is detected (Fig. 5Aa). Sharp and more intense diffraction peaks belonging to MgO (Fig. 5Aa) come from the interaction between the CO gas and Li-RHC-Ti system. The FTIR spectra of both LiBH_4 and Li-RHC-Ti after reaction with pure CO at 400°C (Fig. 5B) show the characteristic bands of the BH_4^- group at 2380 , 2288 , and 2218 cm^{-1} and also at 1282 , 1122 , and 1093 cm^{-1} , which were due to the presence of LiBH_4 . The shoulder at 2485 cm^{-1} can be ascribed to the presence of $\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ cluster, which confirms the presence of some amount of these *closo*-borate phase. On the contrary, for the case of Li-RHC-Ti, the shoulder at 2485 cm^{-1} is much weaker. This fact is related to the presence of Ti-based additive which precludes the

formation of the *closo*-borate phase [51]. The wideband observed in the region 3700-3300 cm^{-1} and the sharp peak at 1629 cm^{-1} are related to O-H stretching vibration and H-O-H. However, this last band can also be attributed to C=O bond, suggesting the formation of formate species. Moreover, the vibration of B-O at 1340 cm^{-1} related to the asymmetric stretching of B-O (three-coordinate boron) was clearly identified after interaction of LiBH_4 with CO [62]. This band is also noted as a shoulder after reaction of Li-RHC-Ti and CO [62].

Figure 5: Characterization after non-isothermal interaction with pure CO (0.27 MPa) up to 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ for the samples in hydrogenated state: **A** XRPD: (a) Li-RHC-Ti, (b) LiBH_4 and (c) MgH_2 . **B** (a) Li-RHC-Ti and (b) LiBH_4 .

To obtain a better mechanistic understanding of the nature of the interaction between CO and MgH_2 , LiBH_4 or Li-RHC-Ti, different gas-phase FTIR spectra as a function of the temperature were taken (Fig. 6 a, b, and c, respectively). Both LiBH_4 and MgH_2 hydrides evidence their ability to reduce CO to CH_4 at 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ in absence of any catalyst, with high selectivity. At this temperature, both hydrides showed progressive decomposition under CO atmosphere (Fig. 4), releasing hydrogen and producing as major residual phases LiH and Mg/MgO, respectively (Fig. 5A). In contrast, the reactivity of Li-RHC-Ti with CO is higher and started at 300 $^\circ\text{C}$: formation of both CH_4 and $\text{B}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ (trimethyl borane) is noticed [63]. The main bands of $\text{B}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ were identified in the 3000-2800 cm^{-1} and 1500-1300 cm^{-1} regions as well as at 1040 cm^{-1} [71]. Moreover, simultaneous CH_3OH presence is apparent, as it can be inferred by the bands at 3100-2800 cm^{-1} ,

1480 cm^{-1} and 1033 cm^{-1} . Thus, production of different gas species by heating of Li-RHC-Ti in CO atmosphere is in correlation with the strong gas absorption observed between 200 °C and 320 °C (Fig. 4). As it is possible to notice by the intensity of the CO FTIR peaks at different temperatures that the reduction of CO *via* the interaction with LiBH_4 is quite notable. For the case of Li-RHC-Ti, the reduction of CO is also noticeable.

Figure 6: FTIR spectra of the gas phases after the isothermal interaction of pure CO (0.1 MPa) with the sample: a) LiBH_4 , b) MgH_2 , c) Li-RHC-Ti (hydrogenated state).

4. Discussion: Dual application of Li-RHC-Ti

Puszkiewicz *et al.* [51] reported a notable improvement on the kinetic behavior of the Li-RHC by the *in situ* formation of core-shell nanostructured Li_xTiO_2 . Under a pure H_2 atmosphere, the Li-RHC + core-shell nanostructured Li_xTiO_2 (Li-RHC-Ti) showed stable hydrogenation and dehydrogenation rates after the 2nd cycle, total hydrogenation and dehydrogenation times of about 25 min and 60 min, respectively, and reversible hydrogen capacities of about 10 wt% [51]. In this work, Fig. 1 shows that the kinetic behavior of the Li-RHC-Ti under pure H_2 slightly differs from the work of Puszkiewicz *et al.* [51]. Under the pure H_2 atmosphere, the stabilization of the reaction rate starts from the 11th cycle. Despite this fact, the overall dehydrogenation times and hydrogen capacities are similar to the already published ones [51]. The observed minor discrepancies between the work of Puszkiewicz *et al.* [51] and this work might be attributed to the change of the starting materials. It was reported that the addition of a tiny amount of TiO_2 to Li-

RHC changes the dehydrogenation pathway at 400 °C and 0.3 MPa of hydrogen overpressure. The change in the dehydrogenation pathway is associated with the formation of core-shell nanoparticles composed of $\text{LiTiO}_2 + \text{Li}_{0.59}\text{TiO}_2$; the crystallographic structure is cubic or tetragonal for the LiTiO_2 , and the one for $\text{Li}_{0.59}\text{TiO}_2$ is orthorhombic. It was found that these core-shell nanostructured Li_xTiO_2 particles are formed *in situ* at the early stage of the hydrogenation-dehydrogenation processes, and they act as Li^+ pumps, thus enhancing the Li^+ mobility and consequently accelerating the kinetic behavior [51]. Although the LiTiO_2 tetragonal phase is an open crystalline lattice and the Li^+ diffusion through liquid LiBH_4 would not be a constraint, the use of a different LiH reagent might modify the rate of the catalyst formation. In this way, its catalytic effect on the dehydrogenation is retarded, and the hydrogenation-dehydrogenation behavior displays a progressive improvement upon cycling (Fig. 1).

In the same line, as seen in Fig. 2, the dehydrogenation time for Li-RHC-Ti cycled under pure H_2 decreases with the number of cycles (faster dehydrogenation). This fact can be ascribed to the gradual formation of the catalytic species owing to the nature of the starting material, as above explained. From Figs. 2 and S1, two relevant facts can be inferred: 1) the first dehydrogenation stage is not dependent on the catalyst formation after cycling in pure H_2 , and 2) CO interacts with the Li-RHC-Ti and/or a product of the reaction (1), decreasing the amount of absorbed hydrogen. In this regard, XRPD analyses after cycling under CO-H_2 and after the interaction with pure CO (Fig. 3A and Fig. 5A) show the formation of MgO for Li-RHC-Ti, suggesting that MgO is mostly formed by an irreversible gas-solid reaction between CO and Mg/ MgH_2 . Hence, one of the reasons for the hydrogen capacity losses during cycling under CO-H_2 mixture (Fig. S1) can be associated with the interaction of CO and Mg to form MgO. Furthermore, the presence of LiBH_4 and MgH_2 in the XRPD (Figs. S2 and 5A) of the Li-RHC-Ti after CO-H_2 /pure CO interactions indicates an incomplete dehydrogenation process. The presence of Mg in the hydrogenated Li-RHC-Ti after pure CO interaction (Fig. 5Aa) suggests that part of the material follows a reaction path towards pure boron [40], which happens when the hydrogen overpressure is low, or the gas atmosphere is inert. FTIR analyses of the solid phase for Li-RHC-Ti after cycling under CO-H_2 (Fig. 3B) and pure CO (Fig. 5B) indicate the formation of borate and formate species. Recent publications

have reported the interaction of alkali borohydride with CO₂ leads to the formation of borate, formate, and methoxy species in the solid or liquid phases [63,64,72–75]. FTIR analyses of the gas phase (Fig. 6c) clearly show the early reactivity (300 °C) of Li-RHC-Ti composites with CO to generate CH₄, among other gases. In the case of the gas-solid interactions of alkali borohydrides with CO₂, different species have been found in the gas phase. Picasso *et al.* observed the formation of methanol and methane in the gas phase as a result of the interaction between KBH₄ and CO₂ upon heating from room temperature to 500 °C [64]. Zhu *et al.*, on the contrary, reported the formation of hydrogen and trimethyl borane from a gas-solid reaction between LiBH₄ and NaBH₄ with CO₂ under mechanochemical conditions [63]. However, there are no previous investigations about the reduction of CO by complex hydrides to produce fuels. In this work, for the first time the reduction of CO using LiBH₄, MgH₂, and Li-RHC was demonstrated.

In order to gain more insight into the reaction mechanism between Li-RHC-Ti and H₂-CO or pure CO, calculations of the phase composition under equilibrium conditions are carried out under the experimental conditions for the systems MgH₂, LiBH₄ and Li-RHC-Ti with pure CO. In these calculations, the catalytic species are not considered. In the ESI the corresponding Tables and Fig. obtained from the calculation outcomes are shown (Tables S1-3 and Figs. S3-5). The interactions of the individual MgH₂ and LiBH₄ with CO lead to the formation of oxides species such as MgO(s) and LiBO₂(s), as well as C(s), in agreement with Figs. 5A and 5Ba. Moreover, the release of H₂(g) and the presence of C(s) suggests that CH₄(g) is formed from a direct reaction, in accordance with the FTIR of the gas phase shown in Figs. 6A and 6B. Thus, for the interactions between MgH₂-CO and LiBH₄-CO the following reactions are proposed:

While the thermodynamics predicts the stable reaction products from the starting materials, the extension of the reaction depends on the experimental conditions used such as partial pressure of H₂ and CO, temperature, contacting time and reactivity of the solid surfaces. Reaction (3) could be represented by the combination of reactions (6) and (7):

On the other hand, MgO could be formed by complete oxidation of MgH₂:

The reactions (7) and (8) have negative Gibbs free energy values in the whole range of temperature. The preferred formation route for MgO is dependent on the different reaction rates of these reactions as a function of the experimental conditions and solid surface reactivity.

In the case of LiBH₄, reaction (4) represents thermodynamic calculations which envision the complete oxidation of LiBH₄ (CO:LiBH₄ ratio of 2:1). However, kinetics factors could restrict the reaction progress. The partial decomposition of LiBH₄ occurs from 300 °C (Fig. 4) releasing H₂ and producing different solid products:

Both reactions are possible because the enthalpy value for reaction (10) is lower than that of reaction (9) [12]. These reactions are in agreement with the formation of LiH and Li₂B₁₂H₁₂ observed after partial decomposition of LiBH₄ in CO atmosphere (Fig. 5A-b). The simultaneous occurrence of reactions (4,5) and (9,10) supports the partial oxidation of LiBH₄ to LiBO₂ (Fig. 5B-a), partial decomposition of LiBH₄ (Fig. 5A-b) and CH₄ formation via hydrogenation of carbon (Fig. 6a).

Calculations on the Li-RHC-CO interactions predict the formation of MgO(s), LiBO₂(s) and C(s), as well as the release of H₂(g) and the formation of CH₄(g) (Table S3 and Fig. S5). These results are in agreement with the behavior of the individual systems MgH₂-CO and LiBH₄-CO and indicate that the interaction of Li-RHC with pure CO leads to the following overall reaction on the solid phase:

Reaction (11) is a combination of reactions (4) and (8). Experimentally, other crystalline phases such as LiH(s), Mg(s) and MgB₂(s) were detected after the Li-RHC-CO interactions by XRPD (Fig. 5A), as well as non-crystalline phases such as formates (HCOO⁻) species by FTIR (Fig. 5B). These species are not predicted by thermodynamic calculations either because of kinetic constraints or the lack of availability of the compound in the database as in the case of the formates. In fact, kinetic restrictions avoid the complete oxidation of both MgH₂ and LiBH₄ to MgO and LiBO₂, respectively (Figs. 5A and 5B) after interaction with pure CO. This result reinforces that MgH₂ and LiBH₄ also reacts simultaneously according to reactions (1) and (2) to produce LiH, MgB₂ and Mg as a competitive processes of reaction (11) during dehydrogenation. For the formed gas-phase during the Li-RHC-CO interaction, reaction (5) can be taken as valid since the formation of CH₄(g) is predicted in agreement with the gas FTIR in Fig. 6c. From the experiments, the production of B(CH₃)₃ (g) and CH₃OH (g) as final products is also detected (Fig. 6c), which deserves additional analysis.

Based on the calculations and experimental results, the interaction between Li-RHC-Ti and CO is catalyzed by the presence of the nanostructured Li_xTiO₂ compounds, leading to the formation of CH₄(g), B(CH₃)₃ (g) and CH₃OH(g) in the gas phase, and MgO, LiBO₂ and formate species in the solid phase. The formation of CH₄ can be attributed to a direct reaction between C(s) produced by oxidation of Li-RHC and H₂(g) released from the hydride species, in agreement with our previous works about the interaction of metallic complex hydrides and CO₂ [34,35]. Moreover, there was previously reported the formation of CH₃OH(g) or B(CH₃)₃(g) by reaction of an alkali metal borohydride with CO₂ [63,64]. Picasso *et al.* observed that the reaction between KBH₄ and CO₂ at temperature higher than 350 °C produces CH₃OH(g) [64]. Zhu *et al.* produced B(CH₃)₃(g) by

mechanochemical solid-gas reaction of LiBH_4 or NaBH_4 with CO_2 . In that investigation, a mechanism involving the interaction between the B atom with the C atom forming B-C bond was proposed, which requires a further step of hydrogenation [63]. In this work it is not clear the mechanism of production of CH_3OH or $\text{B}(\text{CH}_3)_3$, and it deserves further investigations in which the role of the catalyst has to be included.

At the time to analyze the behavior of the Li-RHC-Ti cycled under H_2 -(0.1mol%)CO atmosphere at 400 °C, in Table 1 the equilibrium compositions are shown. Upon hydrogenation, it is possible to see that the formation of a small amount of $\text{CH}_4(\text{g})$ is predicted (0.065 mol%). Taking into account the interactions of Li-RHC-Ti-CO, the formation of CH_4 was experimentally determined (Fig. 6c) and predicted by the calculations (Table 1). Upon dehydrogenation in a free $\text{CO}(\text{g})$ atmosphere, pure $\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ is released, and a considerable amount of the starting species, $\text{MgB}_2(\text{s})$ and $\text{LiH}(\text{s})$ is reversed as it is evidenced in Fig. 1. Moreover, the formation of $\text{MgO}(\text{s})$ as stable species is verified (Fig. 3A).

Therefore, upon cycling of Li-RHC-Ti under CO (0.1 mol%)- H_2 atmosphere, it can be deduced that several reactions are occurring in parallel. During hydrogenation of MgB_2 (reversed reactions 1 and 2), the Mg/MgH_2 formed partially interacts with CO according to reactions (7) and/or (8) by forming $\text{MgO}(\text{s})$ and $\text{C}(\text{s})$, this latter species might quickly react towards the formation of $\text{CH}_4(\text{g})$ (reaction (5)). In addition, LiH instead interacts with part of the $\text{MgB}_2(\text{s})$ and $\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ to form LiBH_4 and as well MgH_2 (reactions (1) and (2)). The experimental evidence also indicates the formation of borates and formates in the solid phase (Fig. 3B), though the amount must be low since the hydrogen capacity is not further reduced (Figs. 1 and S1). Upon dehydrogenation, the atmosphere is clean of $\text{CO}(\text{g})$, hence the pure hydrogen release follows the one predicted by (1) and (2). This proposed mechanism is in the line of the observed reversibility (Fig. 1) of the Li-RHC-Ti composite and its capability to be used as purification system.

v	2LiH + MgB ₂ hydrogenation under 5 MPa CO(0.1 mol%)-H ₂ at 400 °C		2LiBH ₄ +MgH ₂ dehydrogenation at 400 °C	
	Initialcomposition (mol %)	Final composition (mol %)	Initialcomposition (mol %)	Final composition (mol %)
CO ₂ (g)		0		0
C(s)		0		0
CH ₄ (g)		0.065		0
H ₂ (g)	57	52.850		16.7
CO(g)	0.057	0.000		0
LiBH ₄ (s)		5.450	11.7	0.46
LiBO ₂ (s)		0.000		0
LiH(s)	28.63	25.930	55.17	55.23
MgH ₂ (s)		1.600	3.34	0
Mg(s)		1.053	2.24	0
MgO(s)		0.065	0.13	0.11
B ₂ H ₆ (g)		0		0
MgB ₂ (s)	14.315	13.1	27.42	27.5
H ₂ O(g)		0.00		0.00
O ₂ (g)		0.00		0.00
HCOO(g)		0.00		0.00
CH ₃ OH(g)		0.00		0.00
BO ₂ (g)		0.00		0.00
B(CH ₃) ₃ (g)		0.00		0.00

Table 1 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the Li-RHC- Li-RHC-CO(0.1 mol%)-H₂ interactions upon hydrogenation and dehydrogenation at 400 °C. The initial dehydrogenation composition is defined based on the final compositions obtained with the hydrogenation conditions.

Conclusions

A smooth transition from fossil fuel to a renewable energy vector driven society requires materials able to produce synthetic fuels. Moreover, the current and future use of hydrogen as an energy vector in fuel cells demands the availability of high purity of this gas. Li-RHC (2LiH+MgB₂/2LiBH₄+MgH₂) composite doped with TiO₂ (Li-RHC-Ti) has

shown stable and high hydrogen capacity (~ 10 wt%) and notable improved kinetic behavior [51]. The hydrogen absorption/desorption times and the hydrogen storage capacity of the Li-RHC-Ti after repetitive cycles were evaluated at 400 °C under H₂ and H₂-CO atmospheres. A minor decrease of the hydrogen storage capacity of about 4 % after the 11 cycles and gradual degradation of the dehydrogenation rate were measured when the gas atmosphere is changed from pure H₂ to CO-H₂ mixture. XRPD confirmed the formation MgO as one of the major phases obtained after the hydrogenation of the samples, which explains the loss of capacity on account of the irreversible reaction of the Mg/MgH₂ with CO slightly.

Experiments were designed to understand the interaction of Li-RHC-Ti and their individual hydrides with CO, and the characterizations were done by XRPD and FTIR analysis of the solid and gas phases. Based on the thermodynamic calculations and specifically designed experiments, the mechanisms of the main reactions between MgH₂, LiBH₄, and Li-RHC-Ti and CO were proposed. Kinetics constrains, and the occurrence of simultaneous reactions are the main factors that determine the obtained reaction products. In the case of MgH₂, partial oxidation with CO leads to the formation of MgO and Mg, with the simultaneous production of CH₄ and H₂. The system LiBH₄-CO induces the formation of LiH, C, and lithium *closo*-borate as main solid phases with concurrent formation of CH₄ in the gas phase. In the case of dehydrogenation of Li-RHC-Ti under CO, it was demonstrated the formation of MgO, LiBO₂ and HCOO⁻ species as solid products, and co-generation of CH₄, CH₃OH, and B(CH₃)₃ in the gas phase. The presence of Ti-based additive hinders the formation of carbon and *closo*-borate stable species and possibilities the fast-kinetic behavior.

To the best of our knowledge, it is the first time that it is presented the potential of different hydrides such as MgH₂, LiBH₄, and Li-RHC-Ti as reductant agents of CO, as well as the dual ability of Li-RHC-Ti to selectively and reversibly separate impurities from a CO containing hydrogen rich mixture and to reduce this CO into CH₄ based gas mixture. This investigation also demonstrates that metal hydrides-CO systems are a promising alternative for the preparation of gas mixtures based on CH₄.

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Dual application of Ti-catalyzed Li-RHC composite for H₂ purification and CO methanation

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ABSTRACT

2LiH+MgB₂ composite doped with TiO₂ (Li-RHC-Ti) is employed with a two-fold purpose: hydrogen purification under a H₂-CO (0.1 mol %) mixture and CO methanation. Upon dynamic cycling under CO-H₂ mixture, hydrogen release curves display a quite stable amount of pure hydrogen of about 10 wt%, short release times of around 60 min, and minor degradation. Gas analysis by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) after a thermal dehydrogenation process of MgH₂ and LiBH₄ under CO evidence the conversion of CO to CH₄. Li-RHC-Ti dehydrogenated under CO shows the simultaneous formation of CH₄, CH₃OH, and B(CH₃)₃ in the gas phase. X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) and FTIR characterizations of the solid phases of Li-RHC-Ti after both H₂-CO mixture and CO interactions demonstrate the formation of MgO, LiBO₂, and HCOO⁻ species. Li-RHC-Ti acts as a hydrogen source and promoter for the CO conversion. Reaction pathways are proposed based on experimental results and equilibrium composition calculations.

Keywords: Complex Hydrides; Purification; Methanation; Reactive Hydride Composite, Hydrogen

1. Introduction

Hydrogen is a clean and renewable energy source [1]. According to the expected industrial perspectives for 2025, the hydrogen production market will increase,

encouraged by the demand for the use of cleaner energy, such as vehicles with gas-based fuel cells, and by favorable government regulations [2]. Hydrogen is produced primarily from fossil fuels and other alternative routes, such as the electrolysis of water or the use of photobioreactors [3–6]. The technology commonly used in the hydrogen production processes is steam reforming or partial oxidation of natural gases. In the processes that use fossil fuels as hydrogen raw material, minor amounts of contaminants such as CO, CO₂, H₂O, and sulfur compounds are obtained simultaneously as a consequence. For its use in a fuel cell, hydrogen purity is a crucial issue, and it is usually purified to eliminate contaminants and/or impurities [6,7].

While renewable energy sources are inserted as part of our socio-economical system, a smooth transition towards renewable energy vector driven society is unavoidable. Thus, the development of flexible Power-to-Gas and Power-to-Liquid processes for the clean production of currently used energy carriers represents a smart solution for the transition. The energy produced by renewable sources during the low spot energy price periods can be used to reduce H₂O (or H₂O+CO₂) to H₂ or synthetic gas, i.e. H₂+CO, in an electrolyzer or co-electrolyzer, respectively. The synthetic gas can be used as feedstock for synthetic fuels and synthetic chemical production *via* the Fischer-Tropsch process. This allows smartly couple the two major energy infrastructures of our modern society, i.e. gas and electricity networks while covering the necessities of the mobile sector and several industrial demands of feedstock [8,9].

Several metal hydrides have been extensively studied as hydrogen storage materials [10–13]. Since metal hydrides turn out to be safe hydrogen storage materials that selectively absorb hydrogen at a specific temperature and pressure, their use for the separation and/or purification of hydrogen from a gas mixture with impurities would be possible. Therefore, different kinds of hydrides have been investigated for purification of hydrogen from gas mixtures containing impurities as CO, N₂, CO₂, O₂. The main materials studied for separation/purification of hydrogen are related to AB₅-type Laves phases and some AB₂-type alloys [14–26]. However, there are fewer investigations regarding the application of simple metal hydrides and complex hydrides for hydrogen purification. In the past, MgH₂-based materials were explored as possible materials for

hydrogen purification. The hydrogenation/dehydrogenation properties of MgH₂-V composite during cycling under hydrogen-containing carbon monoxide (110 ppm) were evaluated [27]. The MgH₂-V composite showed deterioration on both sorption kinetics and hydrogen storage capacity after prolonged cycling with CO as an impurity. These effects were related to grain surface structure defects and the presence of CO, reducing the activity of the vanadium catalyst due to the formation of MgO_x phases.

In 2007, the first study using amide as a purification system of CO₂-H₂ rich mixtures produced by natural gas reforming was presented. Hu and Ruckenstein studied the interaction between H₂ and CO₂ with Li₃N [28] and LiNH₂-Li₃N [29] as hydrogen storage systems. These authors reported that the CO₂ (20%)-H₂(80%) mixture could be used as a pure hydrogen source for hydrogen storage in a Li-N-H system because the presence of CO₂ had not changed the hydrogen storage properties.

The most recent investigations using amides for hydrogen purification and storage were published by Sun's group and by our group [30–33]. Sun *et al.* studied the effect of various contaminants such as N₂, CH₄, O₂, and CO on the 2LiNH₂-MgH₂ storage system. It was found that impurities as N₂ and CH₄ do not affect neither the hydrogen desorption properties nor the phase structure of the Li-Mg-N-H system. However, other impurities affected: 2LiNH₂-MgH₂ lost hydrogen storage capacity when a mixture of O₂ (0.1 mol %)-H₂ was used due to the formation of LiNH₂ and MgO on the surface of the particle [30]. Furthermore, CO (1 mol %) impurity negatively affected the hydrogen storage properties of this system [31,32]. Already after 5-6 cycles, the dehydrogenation rate decreased, and a loss in the storage capacity was observed, produced by the irreversible loss of [NH₂]⁻ and the MgO formation. The loss of [NH₂]⁻ groups due to the formation of Li₂CN₂ and KCN caused that the hydrogen capacity and hydrogen desorption kinetics could not be restored to its initial level when purified hydrogen was used again [31,32].

Our last results [33] showed that the CO(0.1 mol%)-H₂ mixture made a positive effect on the dehydrogenation rate of the doped Mg(NH₂)₂-2LiH composite after 20 cycles. However, simultaneous and progressive degradation of the hydrogen storage capacity of this material was observed. The formation of Li₂CN₂ and MgO was mainly responsible

for the deterioration of the hydrogen storage properties due to the reaction between pure CO and the dehydrogenated product $\text{Li}_2\text{Mg}(\text{NH})_2$. This interaction was demonstrated with specially designed experiments for the first time. A reactivity order of CO with $\text{LiNH}_2\text{-LiH}$, $\text{Mg}(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{-2LiH}$, and LiBH_4 systems had been established: $[\text{NH}]^{2-} > [\text{NH}_2]^- > [\text{BH}_4]^-$.

We also reported the possibility of employing metal complex hydrides (Mg_2FeH_6 and Mg_2NiH_4) for the production of a synthetic fuel such as CH_4 from CO_2 [34,35]. We demonstrated that metal complex hydrides synthesized via different routes (thermal processes and mechanical milling) are able to act as hydrogen sources and active species for the production of CH_4 . Different methanation mechanisms were obtained depending on of the nature of the complex hydride, its microstructure, $\text{H}_2\text{:CO}_2$ mol ratio and experimental conditions. Fe particles promotes the total CO_2 conversion via a combination of reverse water shift reaction followed by methanation of CO in presence of steam at 400 °C for 5 h [34]. Under same experimental conditions, Mg_2NiH_4 leads to the incomplete transformation of CO_2 via direct reduction of CO_2 by MgH_2 due to the poisoning of Ni catalyst [34]. In contrast, nanometric Mg_2NiH_4 assists the CO_2 conversion in short time in comparison with micrometric Mg_2NiH_4 via the adsorption of C and posterior hydrogenation towards CH_4 [35]. In this context, other authors investigated the mechanochemical hydrogenation of CO carried out over nanostructured FeCo- and Mg_2Ni -based catalysts [36]. The FeCo based catalysts displayed CO conversion data similar or better under mechanochemical conditions (at room temperature) that conventional thermal activation conditions (400–800 K). Improvement in the percentage and kinetics of CO conversion over hydrides was observed that allowed them to gain some hints of the reaction mechanism [36].

Lithium hydride composite (Li-RHC), i.e., $2\text{LiH}+\text{MgB}_2$ or $2\text{LiBH}_4+\text{MgH}_2$ stoichiometric hydride mixture, has been extensively investigated as a hydrogen storage material for practical applications. Li-RHC has a suitable theoretical reaction enthalpy of 46 kJ/mol H_2 , high storage capacity, and an excellent life cycle [12,37–42]. Nevertheless, the dehydrogenation proceeds in two stages according to the reactions (1) and (2), leading to larger enthalpy values [43].

The first stage of the reaction is fast, while the decomposition of LiBH_4 for the formation of MgB_2 is quite slow. Thus, the system has slow kinetic behavior, and for this reason, additives to speed up mainly the second reaction step are required [37,38].

Several studies were done using different additives to improve the hydrogen storage properties of the Li-RHC system. Additives such as transition metals and transition metal compounds (TM-compounds) via the formation of transition metal borides (TM-borides) [44–46], and nanosized TM-borides [47–54] were investigated. Also, the nanoconfinement method, as doped in Li-RHC material, was carried out [55–58]. These catalysts significantly improve the kinetic properties of the system. However, TM-compounds such as halides generate by-products, reducing the hydrogen capacity.

Puszkiet *et al.*[51] showed the effect of the TiO_2 addition to Li-RHC composite and the *in situ* formation of core-shell Li_xTiO_2 nanoparticles. The kinetic behavior and the cycling stability have been noticeably improved with 1 mol % of TiO_2 to Li-RHC. Considering the interesting hydrogen storage properties of catalyzed Li-RHC, the effect of 0.1 mol% of CO in a rich H_2 mixture on the hydrogen storage properties of Li-RHC is investigated in this work. The nature of the interactions between CO and the components of the Li-RHC are here clarified. To the best of our knowledge, the catalytic interaction between Li-RHC and CO has not been reported so far. Furthermore, the main advantages and disadvantages regarding the application of this complex hydride system as hydrogen purification and methanation medium are discussed.

2. Experimental

2.1 Synthesis of the $2\text{LiH} + \text{MgB}_2$ composite with additive

LiH (Aldrich, 95 %, 30 mesh), MgB_2 (Alfa Aesar, 325 mesh) and TiO_2 (Aldrich, 99.99 %) were used as reactants. All materials were handled in a MBraun Unilab argon-filled box, under oxygen and moisture-controlled atmosphere (both levels lower than 5 ppm). Lithium reactive hydride composite $2\text{LiH} + \text{MgB}_2$ was prepared with TiO_2 (1 mol %) as

additive [51] by mechanical milling (MM) for 2 h using a sequence of 15 min milling and 5 min pause. The milling was done in a planetary ball mill (Fritsch Pulverisette 6) at 400 rpm under 0.1 MPa of argon, using an 80 cm³ milling chamber and a ball to powder ratio of 40:1. The sample was named as Li-RHC-Ti (lithium reactive hydride composite with TiO₂ as an additive). Gases of high purity were used, hydrogen (Linde, grade 5.0), argon (Linde, grade 5.0), carbon monoxide (0.1 mol%)-hydrogen mixture (Linde, certificate standard), and carbon monoxide (Praxair, grade 4.5).

2.2 Characterization of the composite

The structure of the Li-RHC-Ti composite and the as-cycled samples was analyzed at room temperature by X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD, PANalytical Empyrean, Cu K α radiation, graphite monochromator) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, Perkin Elmer Spectrum 400 with MCT detector).

For XRPD routine patterns, the samples were maintained under Ar atmosphere using a tightly sealed holder. The data were collected over a 2θ angular range between 10-80° with a step size of 0.02° and a collection time of 1 s. For IR spectroscopy measurements, the solid pellets were prepared under Ar atmosphere inside the glove box using dry KBr and a specially designed airtight cell. FTIR analyses of gas released after heating of LiBH₄, MgH₂, and Li-RHC-Ti composite in pure CO atmosphere at room temperature (RT), 200, 300, and 400 °C were performed. A degassed quartz optical cell with KBr windows was used. The FTIR spectra were collected at RT in the range of 4000-800 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ for solid-state and 0.5 cm⁻¹ for the gas. For the FTIR analyses of gas species, the powders were heated up from room temperature to the desired temperature, kept during 15 min with 0.1 MPa of CO, and then collected in a closed quartz reactor. Finally, the gas atmosphere was expanded into a gas-FTIR cell for the analyses.

For hydrogen sorption kinetics of the Li-RHC-Ti, a modified Sieverts-type device with mass flow controllers was used. The samples were manipulated in a glove box and introduced inside a stainless reactor, which was then connected to the Sieverts equipment. First, the dehydrogenated milled sample was heated up to 400 °C (the reaction temperature) under pure H₂ pressure (5.0 MPa) and kept at this temperature for

15 min. Then, up to 15 dehydrogenation/hydrogenation cycles with pure H₂ were measured as a reference. After cycling with pure H₂, hydrogen storage properties of Li-RHC-Ti were evaluated using a CO (0.1 mol%)-H₂ mixture. Hydrogenation curves were obtained at a constant pressure of 5.0 MPa and dehydrogenation curves with gas backpressure of 0.3 MPa, in both cases at 400 °C. Using the dehydrogenation curves, which consist of two stages, the rate values were obtained. The released hydrogen amounts were expressed as wt%, considering the initial total mass. Moreover, to maximize the possible interactions between the hydrogenated states of the Li-RHC-Ti and CO, its hydrides, i.e., LiBH₄ and MgH₂, were heated with pure CO (0.27 MPa) at 5 °C min⁻¹ from RT to 400 °C. The interactions were displayed as the amount of gas consumed or liberated (gas mol/sample mol) as a function of time.

2.3 Thermodynamic calculations

Calculations on the compositions of species as a product of the hydrides-H₂/CO and hydrides-CO interactions under equilibrium conditions were performed with the software HSC Chemistry 9.7 [59]. Mixtures composed of MgH₂-CO, LiBH₄-CO, Li-RHC-CO, and Li-RHC-H₂-0.1mol%CO were considered. Upon dehydrogenation under pure CO, the equilibrium compositions were calculated with the conditions of a ramp of temperature from 25 °C to 400 °C under 0.27 MPa of CO. In the case of isothermal interaction, 5 MPa of H₂-0.1mol% CO and 400 °C were considered. For the isothermal hydrogenation at 400 °C, as initial compositions, the solid species coming from the hydrogenation outcomes and the removal of the generated gas species upon hydrogenation were taken into account. These conditions are similar to the experimental ones. For all the calculations, species such as closo-borohydrides (Li₂B₁₂H₁₂) and different Mg borates or formate species were not involved since they are not available in the database. Moreover, LiBH₄ is considered as solid-phase over all the temperature range. The following phases were taken into account: LiBH₄(s), MgH₂(s), LiH(s), MgB₂(s), H₂(g), O₂(g), CO(g), CO₂(g), CH₄(g), H₂O(g), B₂H₆(g), HCOO(g), B(CH₃)₃, BO₂(g), CH₃OH(g), C(s), LiBO₂(s), Mg(s), and MgO(s).

3. Results

3.1 Purification of H₂: Li-RHC-Ti cycling under CO (0.1mol%)-H₂ mixture

Li-RHC-Ti composite using pure H₂ or the CO (0.1mol%)-H₂ mixture was studied during continuous cycling. The dehydrogenation cycles obtained under 5.0 MPa of pure H₂ or CO-H₂ mixture at 400 °C are shown in Fig.1. Desorption curves performed under pure H₂ show increasing kinetics from the first until the last cycle (15th cycle). From cycle 11th onwards, the change is not so prominent and it can be considered as it reached a constant desorption rate.

A change in the atmosphere from pure H₂ to CO-H₂ mixture results in different behavior for the Li-RHC-Ti. Fig. 1 shows that the presence of CO during cycling leads to a quite reproducible dehydrogenation kinetic curves and the same hydrogen capacity as the ones obtained with pure H₂.

Figure 1: Dehydrogenation curves of the Li-RHC-Ti at 400 °C after rehydrogenation at 5.0 MPa with pure H₂ and CO (0.1 mol %)-H₂ mixture.

To investigate the effect of CO on the hydrogen storage properties, the evolutions of both the amount of hydrogen released (Fig. S1) and the H₂ desorption times, related with the dehydrogenation rates (Fig. 2), for the first and second reaction steps (equations 1 and 2) were evaluated during cycling. The values of hydrogen storage capacity obtained at 90 min in pure H₂ indicate that the capacity remains stable at 10.1 wt% between the cycles 11 and 15. Under the CO-H₂ mixture, the hydrogen storage capacity of the Li-RHC-Ti slightly decreases with the successive hydrogenation-dehydrogenation cycles. Comparing the hydrogen storage capacities at the end of cycling, a relative reduction of about 4 % in the hydrogen capacity occurs between the sample cycled under pure hydrogen (10.1 wt%, cycle 15) and the one cycled under CO-H₂ mixture (9.7 wt%, cycle 11).

The first stage of the H₂ desorption releases 2 wt%, while the second stage releases from 2 wt% till 10 wt% in total. Fig. 2 shows the time required for the release of half of the hydrogen weight percentage corresponding to each dehydrogenation stage for the Li-RHC-Ti (equations 1 and 2), which provides an estimation of the speed of these processes. For the first dehydrogenation stage, this time remains constant under pure H₂, while it slightly increases under CO-H₂ atmosphere. In contrast, a different behavior was found for the required time in the second dehydrogenation stage. The dehydrogenation time needed to release 6 wt% of Li-RHC-Ti cycled under pure H₂ exhibits a large decrease, meaning a faster desorption rate. On the contrary, the dehydrogenation time for the second stage under the CO-H₂ mixture remains practically constant. Therefore, the presence of 0.1% of CO in the atmosphere has a more marked effect in the first stage, while the second remains practically unchanged.

Figure 2: Time required to achieve 1 and 6 wt% H₂ desorption for the first and second stages, respectively, during each cycle for Li-RHC-Ti. The cycles with CO-H₂ mixture were performed after cycling with pure H₂.

3.2 Characterization of the Li-RHC-Ti and CO-H₂ interactions after cycling

To analyze possible changes in the phases after the interaction between Li-RHC-Ti and the CO containing H₂ atmosphere, XRPD and FTIR spectroscopy measurements were carried out. For comparison purposes, all characterizations were performed with the samples cycled under pure H₂ (see Fig. 3 and S2). No modification of the crystalline phases is found in the dehydrogenated samples, regardless of the presence of CO as an impurity. XRPD analyses are in agreement with the main phases involved in equations (1) and (2), and the employed catalyst (Fig.S2) [51].

Fig. 3A shows the XRPD for the Li-RHC-Ti hydrogenated under 5.0 MPa of pure H₂ and CO-H₂ atmosphere, and at different stages of cycling. In all cases, the main peaks belonging to LiBH₄ and MgH₂ along with reflections corresponding to Li-Ti-O catalytic phases are observed. In particular, small peaks coming from the presence of LiH and MgB₂ are detected after the first hydrogen absorption cycle with pure H₂ (Fig. 3Aa). The formation of MgO upon cycling in pure H₂ can be attributed to a small amount of oxygen in the pipelines and/or the fact that the as-purchased MgB₂ already had small amounts of nanocrystalline MgO (Fig. 3Aa,b). After cycling in pure H₂ or CO-H₂ mixture, it is possible to observe broad peaks of MgO at about 43° and 62° of 2θ. Notably, the MgO peaks display higher intensity in the sample hydrogenated in the presence of CO (Fig. 3Ac).

FTIR technique was used to reveal the possible amorphous compounds in the rehydrogenated samples (Fig.3B). Characteristic stretching and bending modes of the B-H bond at 2380, 2288, 2218, 1122, and 1090 cm⁻¹ are identified for both Li-RHC-Ti cycled under pure H₂ and CO-H₂ mixture (Fig.3Ba,b) [53]. These signals are related to the presence of the LiBH₄ composite, in agreement with the XRPD patterns shown in Fig.3A. An additional band due to the B-H bond can be observed at 2489 cm⁻¹ in both samples that correspond to Li₂B₁₂H₁₂ [60]. Some differences appear when Li-RHC-Ti is cycled in the presence of CO (Fig. 3Bb). The intense signals at 3408 and 1628 cm⁻¹ are ascribed to O-H stretching and (H-O-H) bending vibrations of water molecules over solid [61,62]. The presence of formate species can not be discarded because its main band is overlapped with the band of the bending mode of H-O-H. The FTIR bands at 1384 cm⁻¹ and 1122 cm⁻¹ are related with the formation of B-O bond. The main vibrations of B-O can be observed at 1450-1300 cm⁻¹ and 1150-1000 cm⁻¹ due to asymmetric stretching of three and four coordinate boron, respectively [62]. The formation of borate and formate species was previously reported as products of reactions between borohydrides of alkali metals and CO₂ [63,64]. Bands at low frequencies (600- 700 cm⁻¹) correspond to boron lattice vibrations [65].

Thus, on the base of the XRD and FTIR studies, the reaction between Li-RHC-Ti and CO(1mol%)/H₂ mixture favors the bulk MgO formation as well as the production of

borate and formate species. These results demonstrate that some type of interaction occurred under cycling in presence of CO.

Figure 3: **A** XRPD patterns for Li-RHC-Ti after (a) 1st hydrogenation under 5.0 MPa H₂, (b) 11th rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa H₂ and (c) 12th rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa CO-H₂. **B** FTIR spectra for Li-RHC-Ti after (a) 11th rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa H₂ and (b) 11th rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa CO-H₂. All hydrogenation curves were obtained at 400 °C.

3.3 Methanation of CO: Reactivity between Li-RHC-Ti and pure CO

In this section, the results obtained from the reaction between pure CO and Li-RHC-Ti, as well as with LiBH₄ and MgH₂ are shown. Aiming to shed light on the interactions between Li-RHC-Ti and H₂-CO mixture upon cycling and to investigate the feasibility to employ Li-RHC as the hydrogen source and catalytic compound for the methanation of CO, specific experiments were planned. Volumetric measurements, XRPD analyses, and FTIR spectra of the gas and solid phases were performed to study the reactions.

The gas-solid reaction of CO with Li-RHC-Ti, LiBH₄ and MgH₂ was followed by using a Sieverts equipment and expressed in terms of gas mol/mol of the sample as a function of temperature (Fig. 4, heating from RT to 400 °C). For the case of the LiBH₄ (Fig. 4b) and MgH₂ (Fig. 4c), samples do not show a relevant variation in the amount of gas absorbed up to 300 °C and 360 °C, respectively. LiBH₄ starts to decompose at about 300 °C after 1 h, releasing a final amount of 0.3 mol of gas mol/mol of the sample. MgH₂

begins its decomposition at about 360 °C after about 1 h and 30 min and provides 0.8 mol of gas mol/mol of the sample at the end of the measurement. In the case of the hydrogenated Li-RHC-Ti (Fig. 4a), a CO absorption of about 0.33 mol of gas/mol of sample is observed in the range of temperature between 200 °C and 320 °C. Then, after reaching about 320 °C, the partial decomposition of Li-RHC-Ti starts, and the entire release amounts to 1 mol of gas/mol of sample.

Figure 4: Gas sorption curves as a function of time during non-isothermal interaction of pure CO with (a) Li-RHC-Ti (hydrogenated state), (b) LiBH₄ and (c) MgH₂. Pressure of 0.27 MPa of CO, average heating ramp: 5 °C min⁻¹ from RT to 400 °C (blue dotted line).

Considering the different behavior of Li-RHC-Ti, LiBH₄, and MgH₂ during heating under CO atmosphere, XRPD (Fig. 5A) and FTIR (Fig. 5B) analysis of the solid phases after the volumetric measurements done with pure CO (Fig. 4) were carried out. It is important

to mention that all samples were in hydrogenated state for the heating experiment under CO atmosphere. For pure LiBH_4 sample (Fig.5Ab), the XRPD pattern clearly shows the characteristic peaks of LiBH_4 , simultaneously with the most intense peaks of LiH . Moreover, between 20° and 30° of 2θ it is possible to see a bump attributed to a containing carbon species. It is not clear whether this bump belongs to Li_2C_2 or LiC_6 species, which has been reported as feasible formed phases under the herein working conditions. Both Li_2C_2 and LiC_6 present intense reflections in the above mentioned 2θ , but it seems that they are not in crystalline state, they are in a quite small amount and furthermore peaks of LiBH_4 also present in the same 2θ range [66,67]. Other observable small reflections in the XRPD for LiBH_4 after the heating ramp under CO (Fig. 5Ab) are in the 2θ range between 15° and 18° . These small peaks might come from the presence of crystalline lithium *closo*-borate $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ taking as a reference the work of Pitt et al. [68]. NMR measurements indicated the presence of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ after milling and hydrogen interaction for Li-RHC added $3\text{TiCl}_3\cdot\text{AlCl}_3$, but not in crystalline state [69]. FTIR analyses (Fig. 5B) provides additional information about the carbon and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ species. In the case of MgH_2 , the XRPD pattern (Fig. 5Ac) mainly shows the presence of Mg phase, while the most intense diffraction peaks of MgO and MgH_2 are also observable. Thus, it is possible to find agreement between the volumetric measurement (Fig. 4c) and the detected crystalline phases based on the XRPD patterns: the decomposition of MgH_2 leads to the formation of Mg as the main final phase, while the CO presence induces partial oxidation of MgH_2/Mg to MgO . In the case of the reactive hydride composite exposed to CO, in addition to the presence of the starting materials (LiBH_4 and MgH_2), the formation of Mg , MgB_2 , and MgO is detected (Fig. 5Aa). Sharp and more intense diffraction peaks belonging to MgO (Fig. 5Aa) come from the interaction between the CO gas and Li-RHC-Ti system. The FTIR spectra of both LiBH_4 and Li-RHC-Ti after reaction with pure CO at 400°C (Fig. 5B) show the characteristic bands of the BH_4^- group at 2380 , 2288 , and 2218 cm^{-1} and also at 1282 , 1122 , and 1093 cm^{-1} , which were due to the presence of LiBH_4 . The shoulder at 2485 cm^{-1} can be ascribed to the presence of $\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ cluster, which confirms the presence of some amount of these *closo*-borate phase. On the contrary, for the case of Li-RHC-Ti, the shoulder at 2485 cm^{-1} is much weaker. This fact is related to the presence of Ti-based additive which precludes the

formation of the *closo*-borate phase [51]. The wideband observed in the region 3700-3300 cm^{-1} and the sharp peak at 1629 cm^{-1} are related to O-H stretching vibration and H-O-H. However, this last band can also be attributed to C=O bond, suggesting the formation of formate species. Moreover, the vibration of B-O at 1340 cm^{-1} related to the asymmetric stretching of B-O (three-coordinate boron) was clearly identified after interaction of LiBH_4 with CO [62]. This band is also noted as a shoulder after reaction of Li-RHC-Ti and CO [62].

Figure 5: Characterization after non-isothermal interaction with pure CO (0.27 MPa) up to 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ for the samples in hydrogenated state: **A** XRPD: (a) Li-RHC-Ti, (b) LiBH_4 and (c) MgH_2 . **B** (a) Li-RHC-Ti and (b) LiBH_4 .

To obtain a better mechanistic understanding of the nature of the interaction between CO and MgH_2 , LiBH_4 or Li-RHC-Ti, different gas-phase FTIR spectra as a function of the temperature were taken (Fig. 6 a, b, and c, respectively). Both LiBH_4 and MgH_2 hydrides evidence their ability to reduce CO to CH_4 at 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ in absence of any catalyst, with high selectivity. At this temperature, both hydrides showed progressive decomposition under CO atmosphere (Fig. 4), releasing hydrogen and producing as major residual phases LiH and Mg/MgO, respectively (Fig. 5A). In contrast, the reactivity of Li-RHC-Ti with CO is higher and started at 300 $^\circ\text{C}$: formation of both CH_4 and $\text{B}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ (trimethyl borane) is noticed [63]. The main bands of $\text{B}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ were identified in the 3000-2800 cm^{-1} and 1500-1300 cm^{-1} regions as well as at 1040 cm^{-1} [71]. Moreover, simultaneous CH_3OH presence is apparent, as it can be inferred by the bands at 3100-2800 cm^{-1} ,

1480 cm^{-1} and 1033 cm^{-1} . Thus, production of different gas species by heating of Li-RHC-Ti in CO atmosphere is in correlation with the strong gas absorption observed between 200 °C and 320 °C (Fig. 4). As it is possible to notice by the intensity of the CO FTIR peaks at different temperatures that the reduction of CO *via* the interaction with LiBH_4 is quite notable. For the case of Li-RHC-Ti, the reduction of CO is also noticeable.

Figure 6: FTIR spectra of the gas phases after the isothermal interaction of pure CO (0.1 MPa) with the sample: a) LiBH_4 , b) MgH_2 , c) Li-RHC-Ti (hydrogenated state).

4. Discussion: Dual application of Li-RHC-Ti

Puszkiet *et al.* [51] reported a notable improvement on the kinetic behavior of the Li-RHC by the *in situ* formation of core-shell nanostructured Li_xTiO_2 . Under a pure H_2 atmosphere, the Li-RHC + core-shell nanostructured Li_xTiO_2 (Li-RHC-Ti) showed stable hydrogenation and dehydrogenation rates after the 2nd cycle, total hydrogenation and dehydrogenation times of about 25 min and 60 min, respectively, and reversible hydrogen capacities of about 10 wt% [51]. In this work, Fig. 1 shows that the kinetic behavior of the Li-RHC-Ti under pure H_2 slightly differs from the work of Puszkiet *et al.* [51]. Under the pure H_2 atmosphere, the stabilization of the reaction rate starts from the 11th cycle. Despite this fact, the overall dehydrogenation times and hydrogen capacities are similar to the already published ones [51]. The observed minor discrepancies between the work of Puszkiet *et al.* [51] and this work might be attributed to the change of the starting materials. It was reported that the addition of a tiny amount of TiO_2 to Li-

RHC changes the dehydrogenation pathway at 400 °C and 0.3 MPa of hydrogen overpressure. The change in the dehydrogenation pathway is associated with the formation of core-shell nanoparticles composed of $\text{LiTiO}_2 + \text{Li}_{0.59}\text{TiO}_2$; the crystallographic structure is cubic or tetragonal for the LiTiO_2 , and the one for $\text{Li}_{0.59}\text{TiO}_2$ is orthorhombic. It was found that these core-shell nanostructured Li_xTiO_2 particles are formed *in situ* at the early stage of the hydrogenation-dehydrogenation processes, and they act as Li^+ pumps, thus enhancing the Li^+ mobility and consequently accelerating the kinetic behavior [51]. Although the LiTiO_2 tetragonal phase is an open crystalline lattice and the Li^+ diffusion through liquid LiBH_4 would not be a constraint, the use of a different LiH reagent might modify the rate of the catalyst formation. In this way, its catalytic effect on the dehydrogenation is retarded, and the hydrogenation-dehydrogenation behavior displays a progressive improvement upon cycling (Fig. 1).

In the same line, as seen in Fig. 2, the dehydrogenation time for Li-RHC-Ti cycled under pure H_2 decreases with the number of cycles (faster dehydrogenation). This fact can be ascribed to the gradual formation of the catalytic species owing to the nature of the starting material, as above explained. From Figs. 2 and S1, two relevant facts can be inferred: 1) the first dehydrogenation stage is not dependent on the catalyst formation after cycling in pure H_2 , and 2) CO interacts with the Li-RHC-Ti and/or a product of the reaction (1), decreasing the amount of absorbed hydrogen. In this regard, XRPD analyses after cycling under CO-H_2 and after the interaction with pure CO (Fig. 3A and Fig. 5A) show the formation of MgO for Li-RHC-Ti, suggesting that MgO is mostly formed by an irreversible gas-solid reaction between CO and Mg/ MgH_2 . Hence, one of the reasons for the hydrogen capacity losses during cycling under CO-H_2 mixture (Fig. S1) can be associated with the interaction of CO and Mg to form MgO. Furthermore, the presence of LiBH_4 and MgH_2 in the XRPD (Figs. S2 and 5A) of the Li-RHC-Ti after CO-H_2 /pure CO interactions indicates an incomplete dehydrogenation process. The presence of Mg in the hydrogenated Li-RHC-Ti after pure CO interaction (Fig. 5Aa) suggests that part of the material follows a reaction path towards pure boron [40], which happens when the hydrogen overpressure is low, or the gas atmosphere is inert. FTIR analyses of the solid phase for Li-RHC-Ti after cycling under CO-H_2 (Fig. 3B) and pure CO (Fig. 5B) indicate the formation of borate and formate species. Recent publications

have reported the interaction of alkali borohydride with CO₂ leads to the formation of borate, formate, and methoxy species in the solid or liquid phases [63,64,72–75]. FTIR analyses of the gas phase (Fig. 6c) clearly show the early reactivity (300 °C) of Li-RHC-Ti composites with CO to generate CH₄, among other gases. In the case of the gas-solid interactions of alkali borohydrides with CO₂, different species have been found in the gas phase. Picasso *et al.* observed the formation of methanol and methane in the gas phase as a result of the interaction between KBH₄ and CO₂ upon heating from room temperature to 500 °C [64]. Zhu *et al.*, on the contrary, reported the formation of hydrogen and trimethyl borane from a gas-solid reaction between LiBH₄ and NaBH₄ with CO₂ under mechanochemical conditions [63]. However, there are no previous investigations about the reduction of CO by complex hydrides to produce fuels. In this work, for the first time the reduction of CO using LiBH₄, MgH₂, and Li-RHC was demonstrated.

In order to gain more insight into the reaction mechanism between Li-RHC-Ti and H₂-CO or pure CO, calculations of the phase composition under equilibrium conditions are carried out under the experimental conditions for the systems MgH₂, LiBH₄ and Li-RHC-Ti with pure CO. In these calculations, the catalytic species are not considered. In the ESI the corresponding Tables and Fig. obtained from the calculation outcomes are shown (Tables S1-3 and Figs. S3-5). The interactions of the individual MgH₂ and LiBH₄ with CO lead to the formation of oxides species such as MgO(s) and LiBO₂(s), as well as C(s), in agreement with Figs. 5A and 5Ba. Moreover, the release of H₂(g) and the presence of C(s) suggests that CH₄(g) is formed from a direct reaction, in accordance with the FTIR of the gas phase shown in Figs. 6A and 6B. Thus, for the interactions between MgH₂-CO and LiBH₄-CO the following reactions are proposed:

While the thermodynamics predicts the stable reaction products from the starting materials, the extension of the reaction depends on the experimental conditions used such as partial pressure of H₂ and CO, temperature, contacting time and reactivity of the solid surfaces. Reaction (3) could be represented by the combination of reactions (6) and (7):

On the other hand, MgO could be formed by complete oxidation of MgH₂:

The reactions (7) and (8) have negative Gibbs free energy values in the whole range of temperature. The preferred formation route for MgO is dependent on the different reaction rates of these reactions as a function of the experimental conditions and solid surface reactivity.

In the case of LiBH₄, reaction (4) represents thermodynamic calculations which envision the complete oxidation of LiBH₄ (CO:LiBH₄ ratio of 2:1). However, kinetics factors could restrict the reaction progress. The partial decomposition of LiBH₄ occurs from 300 °C (Fig. 4) releasing H₂ and producing different solid products:

Both reactions are possible because the enthalpy value for reaction (10) is lower than that of reaction (9) [12]. These reactions are in agreement with the formation of LiH and Li₂B₁₂H₁₂ observed after partial decomposition of LiBH₄ in CO atmosphere (Fig. 5A-b). The simultaneous occurrence of reactions (4,5) and (9,10) supports the partial oxidation of LiBH₄ to LiBO₂ (Fig. 5B-a), partial decomposition of LiBH₄ (Fig. 5A-b) and CH₄ formation via hydrogenation of carbon (Fig. 6a).

Calculations on the Li-RHC-CO interactions predict the formation of MgO(s), LiBO₂(s) and C(s), as well as the release of H₂(g) and the formation of CH₄(g) (Table S3 and Fig. S5). These results are in agreement with the behavior of the individual systems MgH₂-CO and LiBH₄-CO and indicate that the interaction of Li-RHC with pure CO leads to the following overall reaction on the solid phase:

Reaction (11) is a combination of reactions (4) and (8). Experimentally, other crystalline phases such as LiH(s), Mg(s) and MgB₂(s) were detected after the Li-RHC-CO interactions by XRPD (Fig. 5A), as well as non-crystalline phases such as formates (HCOO⁻) species by FTIR (Fig. 5B). These species are not predicted by thermodynamic calculations either because of kinetic constraints or the lack of availability of the compound in the database as in the case of the formates. In fact, kinetic restrictions avoid the complete oxidation of both MgH₂ and LiBH₄ to MgO and LiBO₂, respectively (Figs. 5A and 5B) after interaction with pure CO. This result reinforces that MgH₂ and LiBH₄ also reacts simultaneously according to reactions (1) and (2) to produce LiH, MgB₂ and Mg as a competitive processes of reaction (11) during dehydrogenation. For the formed gas-phase during the Li-RHC-CO interaction, reaction (5) can be taken as valid since the formation of CH₄(g) is predicted in agreement with the gas FTIR in Fig. 6c. From the experiments, the production of B(CH₃)₃ (g) and CH₃OH (g) as final products is also detected (Fig. 6c), which deserves additional analysis.

Based on the calculations and experimental results, the interaction between Li-RHC-Ti and CO is catalyzed by the presence of the nanostructured Li_xTiO₂ compounds, leading to the formation of CH₄(g), B(CH₃)₃ (g) and CH₃OH(g) in the gas phase, and MgO, LiBO₂ and formate species in the solid phase. The formation of CH₄ can be attributed to a direct reaction between C(s) produced by oxidation of Li-RHC and H₂(g) released from the hydride species, in agreement with our previous works about the interaction of metallic complex hydrides and CO₂ [34,35]. Moreover, there was previously reported the formation of CH₃OH(g) or B(CH₃)₃(g) by reaction of an alkali metal borohydride with CO₂ [63,64]. Picasso *et al.* observed that the reaction between KBH₄ and CO₂ at temperature higher than 350 °C produces CH₃OH(g) [64]. Zhu *et al.* produced B(CH₃)₃(g) by

mechanochemical solid-gas reaction of LiBH_4 or NaBH_4 with CO_2 . In that investigation, a mechanism involving the interaction between the B atom with the C atom forming B-C bond was proposed, which requires a further step of hydrogenation [63]. In this work it is not clear the mechanism of production of CH_3OH or $\text{B}(\text{CH}_3)_3$, and it deserves further investigations in which the role of the catalyst has to be included.

At the time to analyze the behavior of the Li-RHC-Ti cycled under H_2 -(0.1mol%)CO atmosphere at 400 °C, in Table 1 the equilibrium compositions are shown. Upon hydrogenation, it is possible to see that the formation of a small amount of $\text{CH}_4(\text{g})$ is predicted (0.065 mol%). Taking into account the interactions of Li-RHC-Ti-CO, the formation of CH_4 was experimentally determined (Fig. 6c) and predicted by the calculations (Table 1). Upon dehydrogenation in a free $\text{CO}(\text{g})$ atmosphere, pure $\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ is released, and a considerable amount of the starting species, $\text{MgB}_2(\text{s})$ and $\text{LiH}(\text{s})$ is reversed as it is evidenced in Fig. 1. Moreover, the formation of $\text{MgO}(\text{s})$ as stable species is verified (Fig. 3A).

Therefore, upon cycling of Li-RHC-Ti under CO (0.1 mol%)- H_2 atmosphere, it can be deduced that several reactions are occurring in parallel. During hydrogenation of MgB_2 (reversed reactions 1 and 2), the Mg/MgH_2 formed partially interacts with CO according to reactions (7) and/or (8) by forming $\text{MgO}(\text{s})$ and $\text{C}(\text{s})$, this latter species might quickly react towards the formation of $\text{CH}_4(\text{g})$ (reaction (5)). In addition, LiH instead interacts with part of the $\text{MgB}_2(\text{s})$ and $\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ to form LiBH_4 and as well MgH_2 (reactions (1) and (2)). The experimental evidence also indicates the formation of borates and formates in the solid phase (Fig. 3B), though the amount must be low since the hydrogen capacity is not further reduced (Figs. 1 and S1). Upon dehydrogenation, the atmosphere is clean of $\text{CO}(\text{g})$, hence the pure hydrogen release follows the one predicted by (1) and (2). This proposed mechanism is in the line of the observed reversibility (Fig. 1) of the Li-RHC-Ti composite and its capability to be used as purification system.

v	2LiH + MgB ₂ hydrogenation under 5 MPa CO(0.1 mol%)-H ₂ at 400 °C		2LiBH ₄ +MgH ₂ dehydrogenation at 400 °C	
	Initialcomposition (mol %)	Final composition (mol %)	Initialcomposition (mol %)	Final composition (mol %)
CO ₂ (g)		0		0
C(s)		0		0
CH ₄ (g)		0.065		0
H ₂ (g)	57	52.850		16.7
CO(g)	0.057	0.000		0
LiBH ₄ (s)		5.450	11.7	0.46
LiBO ₂ (s)		0.000		0
LiH(s)	28.63	25.930	55.17	55.23
MgH ₂ (s)		1.600	3.34	0
Mg(s)		1.053	2.24	0
MgO(s)		0.065	0.13	0.11
B ₂ H ₆ (g)		0		0
MgB ₂ (s)	14.315	13.1	27.42	27.5
H ₂ O(g)		0.00		0.00
O ₂ (g)		0.00		0.00
HCOO(g)		0.00		0.00
CH ₃ OH(g)		0.00		0.00
BO ₂ (g)		0.00		0.00
B(CH ₃) ₃ (g)		0.00		0.00

Table 1 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the Li-RHC- Li-RHC-CO(0.1 mol%)-H₂ interactions upon hydrogenation and dehydrogenation at 400 °C. The initial dehydrogenation composition is defined based on the final compositions obtained with the hydrogenation conditions.

Conclusions

A smooth transition from fossil fuel to a renewable energy vector driven society requires materials able to produce synthetic fuels. Moreover, the current and future use of hydrogen as an energy vector in fuel cells demands the availability of high purity of this gas. Li-RHC (2LiH+MgB₂/2LiBH₄+MgH₂) composite doped with TiO₂ (Li-RHC-Ti) has

shown stable and high hydrogen capacity (~ 10 wt%) and notable improved kinetic behavior [51]. The hydrogen absorption/desorption times and the hydrogen storage capacity of the Li-RHC-Ti after repetitive cycles were evaluated at 400 °C under H₂ and H₂-CO atmospheres. A minor decrease of the hydrogen storage capacity of about 4 % after the 11 cycles and gradual degradation of the dehydrogenation rate were measured when the gas atmosphere is changed from pure H₂ to CO-H₂ mixture. XRPD confirmed the formation MgO as one of the major phases obtained after the hydrogenation of the samples, which explains the loss of capacity on account of the irreversible reaction of the Mg/MgH₂ with CO slightly.

Experiments were designed to understand the interaction of Li-RHC-Ti and their individual hydrides with CO, and the characterizations were done by XRPD and FTIR analysis of the solid and gas phases. Based on the thermodynamic calculations and specifically designed experiments, the mechanisms of the main reactions between MgH₂, LiBH₄, and Li-RHC-Ti and CO were proposed. Kinetics constrains, and the occurrence of simultaneous reactions are the main factors that determine the obtained reaction products. In the case of MgH₂, partial oxidation with CO leads to the formation of MgO and Mg, with the simultaneous production of CH₄ and H₂. The system LiBH₄-CO induces the formation of LiH, C, and lithium *closo*-borate as main solid phases with concurrent formation of CH₄ in the gas phase. In the case of dehydrogenation of Li-RHC-Ti under CO, it was demonstrated the formation of MgO, LiBO₂ and HCOO⁻ species as solid products, and co-generation of CH₄, CH₃OH, and B(CH₃)₃ in the gas phase. The presence of Ti-based additive hinders the formation of carbon and *closo*-borate stable species and possibilities the fast-kinetic behavior.

To the best of our knowledge, it is the first time that it is presented the potential of different hydrides such as MgH₂, LiBH₄, and Li-RHC-Ti as reductant agents of CO, as well as the dual ability of Li-RHC-Ti to selectively and reversibly separate impurities from a CO containing hydrogen rich mixture and to reduce this CO into CH₄ based gas mixture. This investigation also demonstrates that metal hydrides-CO systems are a promising alternative for the preparation of gas mixtures based on CH₄.

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Species	2LiH + MgB ₂ hydrogenation under 5 MPa CO(0.1 mol%)-H ₂ at 400 °C		2LiBH ₄ +MgH ₂ dehydrogenation at 400 °C	
	Initialcomposition (mol %)	Final composition (mol %)	Initialcomposition (mol %)	Final composition (mol %)
CO ₂ (g)		0		0
C(s)		0		0
CH ₄ (g)		0.065		0
H ₂ (g)	57	52.850		16.7
CO(g)	0.057	0.000		0
LiBH ₄ (s)		5.450	11.7	0.46
LiBO ₂ (s)		0.000		0
LiH(s)	28.63	25.930	55.17	55.23
MgH ₂ (s)		1.600	3.34	0
Mg(s)		1.053	2.24	0
MgO(s)		0.065	0.13	0.11
B ₂ H ₆ (g)		0		0
MgB ₂ (s)	14.315	13.1	27.42	27.5
H ₂ O(g)		0.00		0.00
O ₂ (g)		0.00		0.00
HCOO(g)		0.00		0.00
CH ₃ OH(g)		0.00		0.00
BO ₂ (g)		0.00		0.00
B(CH ₃) ₃ (g)		0.00		0.00

Table 1 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the Li-RHC- Li-RHC-CO(0.1 mol%) H₂ interactions upon hydrogenation and dehydrogenation at 400 °C. The initial dehydrogenation composition is defined based on the final compositions obtained with the hydrogenation conditions.

Figure 2
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Figure 5

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Figure 6
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Figure1

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